
SCOPE OF WORK

MARKET MAPPING & ASSESSMENT STUDY FOR JORDANIAN HORTICULTURE

Rami Jacob Kakish

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A) Scope of Work.

Purpose and Objective

This study aims to identify viable market opportunities for farmers in Jordan. The market mapping will be based on analyzing demand, consumer behavior, competitive dynamics, marketing channels, knowledge gaps, market access and entry barriers.

Based on the aforementioned findings, the study key objectives of intervention strategies:

- Support Jordanian farmers in accessing high-demand markets.
- Close the knowledge gaps whether in post or pre harvest activities, by segment-tailored **coaching sessions and training programs**, which enable smallholders to improve market access, competitiveness, and eventually profitability and income.

1. Approach

The agro-food systems in Jordan are facing tremendous changes most specifically in market systems, wholesale sector, retail sector and capital size, the latter contributes to segmentation of producers increasingly into two different strata: big producers and small holder farmers.

This report acknowledges that the market functions as central mechanism for social differentiation that widens the gap between big producers and small producers (with relatively weak market access). Theoretically big producers have less market related issues and for a specific socio-economic criterion that differentiates small holder farmers this report aims to identify market opportunities, knowledge gaps market accessibility in order to design coaching and training programs to improve market access for farmers in Jordan.

As previously mentioned, the main objective of this study revolves around designing intervention strategies to improve farm-income and associated farmers' livelihoods. Such interventions are expected to inform the design of coaching sessions and training material that are **market-centered** and identify market opportunities and thus require a comprehensive market mapping and assessment to guide the design of the associated training and coaching session.

Key components for market-mapping centered coaching and training:

1. Market Demand and Consumer Behavior Analysis

- Objective: Understand consumer preferences, identify cash-crops, and identify seasonal demand patterns.
- Outcome: provide farmers with a crop rotation plan and crop varieties that best identify consumer needs and farmer profitability.

2. Market channels

- Objective: Identify key post-harvest marketing channels, and farmer profitability per channel such as: Farm gate, central markets, contractors, export markets.
- Outcome: understand the profitability per channel and which channel constitutes opportunities for increased profit and which are underutilized.

3. Competition and pricing dynamics

- Objective: access production landscape and identify “Model farms” that are know for best practices and best profitability in the market to help farmers set competitive prices and meet the demanded quality.
- Outcome: Improved knowledge of *competitive positioning, pricing trends and market entry through abiding to the demanded quality.*

4. Market access and barriers

- Objective: mapping barriers for the targeted farmers group in means of the following barriers regulatory, infrastructural, logistics, market entry (Standards and certifications), and transaction cost.
- Outcome: Recommend solutions to overcome the mentioned barriers with solutions such as: improved documentation and certification, quality standards compliance, transportation. ...etc.

5. Training to bridge the knowledge and skill gaps.

- Objective: Based on market insights, design segment-tailored coaching sessions and training programs to address specific knowledge gaps, from post-harvest handling to marketing skills.
- Outcome: Enhance farmers’ market readiness and competitiveness by closing skill gaps that impact market performance.

2. Methodology: Data Collection and associated stakeholders

To conduct the nuanced market mapping study of Jordanian horticulture, first a narrative and overall market structure shall be drawn using publicly available data (secondary market research) to map market, sector and overall contribution of crops to GDP and livelihood of farmers. This data shall be cited by desk researching the below sources under the below category **Secondary data sources**. This will typically allow us to find the following:

- Macro-economic overview
- Horticulture market overview
- regulatory framework
- Producers typers and segmentations
- estimated crop earnings.

Secondary data sources:

1. Local Directorates and Authorities statistics and industry reports

Department of Statistics (DOS) - National Account (I/O Tables, supply use tables: intersectoral economic linkages data on horticulture).

DOS - Crops Statistics – Agricultural Prices – Food Budget – HEIS

2. **International Organizations** (World bank. WEF database. FAO and IFPRI)
3. **International, local NGO, and famers unions** (ICARDA, IFPRI Jordan Farmers Union, Jordanian Citrus Agri Coop. Society, Water User Associations).

Primary data sources for the study will include the following stakeholders to collect data from (using various methods: farmers surveys, consumer surveys, and focus groups...etc.):

Smallholder farmers, agricultural cooperatives, and Water User Associations provide access to big producers in Jordan valley, supported by research bodies like NARC, APN, and RSCN. Central and wholesale markets (e.g., Amman Municipality) contribute data on product flow and pricing. Key partners include government representatives (e.g., Ministry of Agriculture), NGOs (e.g., Phenix, Tamkeen), international organizations (IFPRI, ICARDA, FAO), and academia for expertise and resources.

The table below summarizes the stakeholders, data collection methods, and type of market research:

Category	Specific Data	Involved Stakeholders	Data Collection Purpose	Data Collection Method
Market Demand & Consumer Behavior	- High-demand crops, seasonal demand patterns. - Consumer preferences for product attributes (e.g., packaging, organic, quality standards).	- Retailers (local markets, supermarkets) - Wholesalers - Consumers	Identify high-demand products and align farmers' production with market needs.	Surveys and Interviews - Consumer Surveys - FAO reports
Market channels	Market channels typers, trade distribution and profitability per channel (e.g. export, wholesale, contractors...etc.)	- Famers - Wholesalers - NGOs - Exporters And - Farmers' cooperatives	Identify profit opportunities in underutilized marketing channels	Desk research surveys and interviews - World Bank reports - DOS Agricultural Prices and Crops Statistics
Competitive Landscape & Pricing	- Pricing trends across different market channels (e.g., wholesale, retail). - Competitor positioning and quality benchmarks.	- Competitors (local farmers, cooperatives) - Market analysts - Agrarian organizations (local and international)	Assess pricing strategies and help farmers set competitive prices and quality standards based on demand.	Secondary Research (reports, databases)
Market Access Barriers	-Logistics constraints (e.g., transport costs, storage availability). - Regulatory requirements and documentation	- Logistics providers - Regulatory agencies (Ministry of Agriculture, customs)	identify barriers that limit market access for farmers, providing solutions for entry and compliance	Interviews with stakeholders; Regulatory documents (secondary)

	(e.g., certifications, organic...etc.).			
Socio-Economic Constraints	-Resource and financial access (e.g., credit, subsidies). - Key challenges faced by farmers, including technology literacy.	- Farmers - Local financial institutions (banks, Agri credit cop, micro credit inst...etc.)	Interviews and Focus Groups (Primary) - IFPRI and ICARDA publications (secondary)	Financial and tech knowledge needs improved market readiness.
Infrastructure and Support Service	Availability of post-harvest support services (e.g., quality control, packaging, Cold storage).	- Local municipalities (Amman Municipality) - Farmers	Interviews & Secondary Research	Gap in support services needed to improve product marketability.
Marketing Strategies & Outreach	-Marketing strategies, including direct vs. indirect channels. - Communication (e.g., digital presence, branding)	- NGOs and Cooperatives - Farmers' associations (Jordan Farmers Union)	Focus Groups and Case Studies	Training in marketing techniques that increase visibility and consumer engagement .

B) Tentative structure for Mapping report

Management Summary

Overview of market opportunities, barriers, and actionable recommendations for Jordanian farmers.

1. Introduction

1.1 General overview of characteristics and trends of the Jordanian Horticulture and Agriculture sector and market systems.

1.2 Key food and non-food (ornamental) crops

2. Approach and Methodology

study's approach (market mapping and data collection focus) and methodology used, including data sources, stakeholder engagement, and specific data collection methods.

3. Market Overview

3.1 **General characteristics and trends of the Jordanian Horticulture and Agriculture sector:** market size, demand trends, and market structures.

3.2 **Key food and non-food (ornamental) crops and Market Segments:** overview of horticultural crops, including major product groups and market segments.

4. Market Analysis

4.1 *The Jordanian (Domestic) Horticulture market*

- 4.1.1 Market segmentation and product groups
- 4.1.2 Consumer and Market Trends
- 4.1.3 Trends in trade and legislation

4.2 *Regional markets (Or potential and current export markets)*

4.3 *Trade flows*

- 4.3.1 Jordan exports
- 4.3.2 Jordan imports

4.4 Main competitors and seasonal patterns

5. Market Access Barriers and Bottlenecks

5.1 Overview of Market Access Challenges

5.2 Market Segmentation: Smallholders vs. Large Producers.

5.3 Human capital: Capacity gaps

5.4 Transport margins and transaction costs.

5.5 Technology & production input

5.6 Legislation and policy barriers

5.7 Summary of Key Market Bottlenecks

6. Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

6.2 Human Resources - Capacity Building and Development

6.2.1 Coaching and training sessions

6.2.2 Sustainable advisory and knowledge base.

6.2.3 Refugees' inclusion

6.3 Technology & production input

6.4 Business and market environment

6.5 Summary and outlook

Rami Kakish

kakishrami@outlook.com

+96277603191, +4915739810796